

AAEA-CNSTN workshop summary: "Development of irradiated vaccines", 16–20/09/2024, Republic of Tunisia

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Abstract

This report presents a comprehensive summary of the objectives, content, and outcomes of the "Development of Irradiated Vaccines" workshop, jointly organized by the Arab Atomic Energy Agency (AAEA) and the National Center for Nuclear Sciences and Technology (CNSTN), with the support of various organisations like the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), the U.S. Department of Energy/National Nuclear Security Administration (DOE/NNSA), and CRDF Global, held from 16–20 September 2024 in the Republic of Tunisia. In addition to the course co-director representing the AAEA and the local course director, a total of 14 esteemed experts from various countries contributed to the workshop on topics related to the development and quality control of irradiated vaccines, including virus-like particle (VLP)-based vaccines produced using radiation-inducible promoters. Among them, six were local trainers, three international trainers attended in person, while the remaining five experts delivered their sessions remotely. The workshop has attracted a diverse group of 22 participants, with 15 from Tunisia and 7 from other Arabic countries such as Iraq, Libya, Mauritania, Saudi Arabia, and Syria. This includes a group of 7 male and 15 female participants, spanning birth years from 1966 to 1998. Unfortunately, several participants from Algeria, Egypt, Jordan, and Yemen could not join due to various constraints. The goals of this workshop are to facilitate knowledge sharing among experts and participants, introduce advanced techniques in the development of irradiated vaccines, strengthen partnerships among the participating countries and organizations, and enhance regional capacity for the development of such vaccines.

Workshop summary

AAEA mission

Tarek Elmaghraby, the Arab Atomic Energy Agency (AAEA) coordinator and course co-director, presented the activities of the AAEA. As a regional specialized organization operating under the League of Arab States, the AAEA coordinates the scientific efforts of Arab countries in the peaceful applications

of atomic energy. A key function of the AAEA is to facilitate the transfer of nuclear knowledge and technologies for peaceful purposes. Additionally, one of its most significant roles is to foster collaboration among Arab states by promoting the shared use of laboratory facilities and the development of human resources capable of assimilating and applying nuclear knowledge.

Overview of the workshop agenda

Haïtham Sghaier, professor of biological engineering (specializing in cellular and molecular bioengineering, radiation, and computational microbiology) at the National Center for Nuclear Sciences and Technology (CNSTN), Tunisia, was the local coordinator and course co-director of the workshop. He is also the project counterpart (PCP) for a technical cooperation project (TUN5032) and the chief scientific investigator (CSI) for a coordinated research project (CRP 2296, Project Code: D32037, Contract Number: 26187), about irradiated vaccines, funded by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). He provided an overview of the workshop, outlining its objectives, trainers, and participants.

He highlighted three key reasons for the workshop's significance: (1) the historical impact of pandemics, from the Plague of Justinian in 541–542 A.D. to the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, underscores the critical need for continued efforts in developing effective vaccines; (2) irradiated vaccines present a promising approach to vaccine development by using radiation to inactivate pathogens while preserving their immunogenic properties, a field that has gained renewed interest due to advancements in irradiation technology and a deeper understanding of immune responses; and (3) to his knowledge, Tunisia is the only country in the Arab region currently engaged in the development of irradiated vaccines, supported by ongoing IAEA projects (<http://www.aquavac-ir.tn/>).

Keynote: Irradiation technologies for vaccine development

Viskam Wijewardana obtained his PhD in Veterinary Immunology from Osaka Prefecture University, Japan in 2007 and BVSc from the University of

Peradeniya, Sri Lanka in 1999. He was a Post Doctoral Associate at the University of Pittsburgh with Simon Barratt-Boyes, Ivona Pandrea and Cristian Apetrei on the areas of SIV/HIV immunology 2007–2012. He was a research fellow at Osaka Prefecture University working on Dendritic cell-based cancer immunotherapy 2012–2014. Since 2015, he is working at the IAEA in Vienna and currently the Head of the Animal Production and Health (APH) Laboratory.

Irradiation functions by inducing damage to the genetic material of pathogens, thereby inhibiting their ability to replicate while preserving their metabolic activity. This process yields "metabolically active, non-replicating" microorganisms capable of eliciting a potent immune response. Recent research has demonstrated that such vaccines can effectively induce both humoral and cellular immunity, which are essential for protection against a broad spectrum of diseases ((Wijewardana et al., 2022) and references therein).

In the development of irradiated vaccines, various irradiation technologies are employed for pathogen inactivation. Gamma irradiation, traditionally used for this purpose, is effective but presents safety challenges and requires specialized facilities. Electron beam (e-beam) irradiation, a more recent innovation, offers faster processing, making it more practical for large-scale vaccine production. X-ray irradiation is emerging as a viable alternative, capable of delivering effective pathogen inactivation doses without the complications associated with radioactive materials ((Wijewardana et al., 2022) and references therein).

Viskam Wijewardana was unable to deliver the keynote inaugural speech due to scheduling overlapping engagements with another event at the IAEA. This information was conveyed by Richard Kangethe during the workshop.

Practical applications and immunological evaluation of irradiated livestock vaccines: Sample processing and technique analysis

Richard Kangethe earned his PhD in Biochemistry, specializing in molecular parasitology, from the University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa, in 2012.

Following the completion of his doctoral studies, he served as a postdoctoral researcher at the HIV Pathogenesis Program located within the Nelson R. Mandela School of Medicine at the University of KwaZulu-Natal. His research focused on elucidating the relationship between HIV and *Cryptococcus meningitis* in antiretroviral therapy-naive patients. In November 2012, he was appointed as a consultant at the IAEA laboratories in Seibersdorf, where he initiated studies investigating the effects of low-dose irradiation on *Trypanosoma* spp. In 2017, he transitioned to the role of animal health technician, where he currently develops molecular tools for livestock immunology and irradiated vaccine studies. He has conducted research on a diverse array of livestock samples, including avian, ruminant, porcine, and fish, focusing on diseases caused by viral, bacterial, and parasitic agents.

During this workshop, he provided training on several practical aspects, including: (1) irradiation of livestock vaccines and immunological evaluation (Session I); (2) processing samples from various sources; and (3) analysis and interpretation of different techniques. His first lecture emphasised on identifying the different parameters that need to be defined on preparing irradiated vaccines depending on whether the disease targeted was viral, bacterial, or parasitic and the different methods available for antigen protection during and after irradiation. His next two lectures defined how to test for antigenicity *ex vivo* using cells from various tissues in different animals. This included describing the development of a monocyte derived dendritic cell assay for antigen presentation used for screening potential vaccine candidates before attempting any *in vivo* vaccination studies. He also described post-vaccination and pre-challenge monitoring of interleukins, pathogen recognition receptors and cell surface markers, all hallmarks of cell-mediated and innate immunity using qPCR and flow cytometry.

Electron beam based rapid and continuous pathogen inactivation — A new perspective for the manufacturing of whole-inactivated vaccines

Daniel Becker holds a Master of Science degree in Industrial Biotechnology, with a specialization in bioprocess technologies and process optimization, from the University of Ulm and the University of Applied Sciences Biberach in

Germany, graduating in 2018. In 2019, he joined the Laboratory Automation and Bioproduction Technology department at Fraunhofer IPA in Stuttgart. During his tenure, he contributed to various public and industrial projects, notably authoring a strategic report for the Bausch + Ströbel Group, which was instrumental in establishing the spin-off company KyooBe Tech GmbH, where he assumed the role of Project Lead. Since 2020, Mr. Becker has been at the forefront of the INACTIVATE lighthouse project, which focuses on the development of next-generation vaccine manufacturing technologies utilizing electron beam technology. In 2023, he took on the position of Head of Business Development for Project INACTIVATE, where he has successfully initiated significant networking activities. He serves as the primary customer liaison, leading the strategic positioning and alliance formation for the eFIT product line. In this capacity, Mr. Becker collaborates closely with key partners, including Fraunhofer IZI, across Germany and Europe, to provide an integrated approach encompassing research, development, and manufacturing of irradiated vaccines.

In this workshop, in addition to delivering a theoretical session titled "Electron beam-based rapid and continuous pathogen inactivation: A new perspective for the manufacturing of whole-inactivated vaccines," he also conducted a practical session on "The long journey towards commercialization: Lessons learned from over a decade of R&D with electron beams in the field of pathogen inactivation." The key "take-home" messages from his sessions included: (1) Low-Energy Electron Irradiation (LEEI) is a highly effective method for the continuous and rapid irradiation of liquid materials. (2) This technique provides a precise means of inactivating specific pathogens in liquids, making it particularly valuable for generating irradiated vaccines from pathogen-containing liquids. (3) LEEI offers a universal inactivation approach that is capable of targeting a wide range of pathogens, including protozoa, bacteria, and viruses. (4) Various liquid-processing technologies can be employed to inactivate pathogens using LEEI, with microfluidics emerging as the most advantageous for our purposes. (5) After years of collaborative research, this technology is now market-ready.

Comprehensive training on microbial inactivation and vaccine development utilizing high electron beam irradiation

Chandni Praveen is a research scientist at the National Center for Electron Beam Research (NCEBR), Texas A&M University. She is the lead scientist handling the vaccine development portfolio of NCEBR aiming to generate bacterial and viral vaccines that are important for both human and animal health. She has extensive research expertise in developing and characterizing electron beam inactivated vaccines and immunomodulators against key pathogens such as *Salmonella* Typhimurium, *Salmonella* Enteritidis and *Clostridium perfringens*. Her research focuses on understanding the biological response to inactivation and developing sustainable substitutes for radioactive isotope-based irradiation methods for microbial inactivation. She received her doctoral degree in Toxicology from Texas A&M University in 2014. Her doctoral dissertation was "Electron beam as a next generation vaccine platform: Microbiological and immunological characterization of an electron beam based vaccine against *Salmonella* Typhimurium". She identified the metabolically active yet non culturable (MAyNC) stages of eBeam inactivated bacteria and assessed their immunostimulatory potential. She serves as the Facility-in-Charge of a BSL-3 laboratory, Pune Bio cluster at the National Centre for Cell Sciences in India where she was involved in the development of the Biosafety Level -3 laboratory core facility for working with high-risk group pathogens. During the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic period, she served as the Laboratory in-Charge of Virus Research and Diagnostics Centre (VRDC) at Inter University Centre for Biomedical Research, MG University, Kerala, India. Under her leadership, VRDC became an active member of the National and State level COVID-19 pandemic response program for SARS-CoV-2 diagnostics from clinical samples for the Government of India and the Kerala State Health Department. Currently, she is involved in comparative evaluation of Machine Source based Radio Vaccine Development Strategies such as High (HEEB), Medium (MEEB), Low-energy Electron Beam (LEEB) and X-ray with legacy technologies such as cobalt-60 based gamma irradiation for identifying the viable alternatives to gamma-based vaccine development.

She conducted five training sessions: (1) basic understanding of microbial inactivation using electron beam irradiation; (2) practical session — Determination of microbial decimal reduction dose (D_{10} value) of specific microorganisms; (3) developing irradiated vaccines using high-energy electron beam; (4) practical session — Evaluation of antigenicity and vaccine efficacy of irradiated vaccines — Practical aspects; and (5) case studies on specific irradiated bacterial and viral vaccines. The key "take-home" messages from her sessions included: (1) principle mechanisms involved in microbial irradiation by ionizing irradiation; (2) step by step methodology for determining the microbial inactivation kinetics using linear regression analysis and interpreting the D-10 value with respect to developing irradiated vaccines; (3) roadmap for developing and characterizing irradiated bacterial and viral vaccines using HEEB; (4) different techniques used in immunological characterization of irradiated vaccines and assessment of the vaccine efficacy and protection imparted using various animal model systems; and (5) applications of HEEB technology for microbial irradiation aiming to develop tools for active and passive immunization.

Advancements in irradiated vaccines and methods for attenuation of protozoan and helminth parasites

Eric R James obtained his B.Sc. in Zoology from the University of London, a M.Sc. in Medical Parasitology from the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (LSHTM), and Ph.D. in Immunity to Helminths also from LSHTM. An appointment as Lecturer in the Department of Helminthology at LSHTM followed, with his research based at the LSHTM Winches Farm Field Station in St. Albans. This appointment was to work in Martin Taylor's group on a Rockefeller Foundation-funded project titled "Towards the development of a live vaccine against schistosomiasis" using radiation-attenuated schistosome cercariae as the vaccine immunogen. He developed a method to transform *in vitro* the cercaria to (the post-penetration) schistosomulum stage, helped to define the optimum radiation dose, identified the intramuscular route as the optimal route for administration, and then developed a cryopreservation method for the schistosomula under the tutelage of the eminent cryobiologist John Farrant at the Medical Research Council's Cryobiology Division. The

cryopreservation work expanded to include many other parasitic helminth species, protozoa (including *Leishmania* and *Plasmodium*), hepatocytes and other cells. In 1984, he moved to the Storm Eye Institute at the Medical University of South Carolina (MUSC), in Charleston, SC, U.S.A. to work on the parasitic filarial disease, River Blindness. At MUSC, his work focused on antigen discovery for onchocerciasis vaccine development, studying parasite antioxidant enzymes and cryptic/hidden antigens. And latterly included work on steroid-induced cataract, and apoptosis, particularly as this relates to cataract development and parasitic infections. The cryobiology thread continued at MUSC with the successful cryopreservation of *Neoaplectana*, a nematode parasite of agricultural insect pests, and *Trichinella*. In 2007, He moved to Sanaria Inc in Rockville, MD to work on the cryopreservation of *Plasmodium falciparum* sporozoites — the immunogen in the radiation-attenuated PfSPZ Vaccine. At Sanaria, he has developed the radiation-attenuation, fill-finish (vialing, capping, sealing and a new novel cryovial with integral septum), cryopreservation, storage, distribution logistics, thawing of vaccine cryovials in the clinic and syringe preparation components of PfSPZ products.

In this workshop, he conducted three training sessions: (1) irradiated vaccines against protozoan and helminth parasites; (2) practical session — Attenuation of parasites: methods, assays; and (3) methods development in irradiation of helminth and protozoan parasite attenuation. Additionally, he included a session on (4) the thermostabilization of whole live-attenuated vaccine immunogens, focussing on cryopreservation technology and practical aspects. The key "take-home" messages from his sessions included: (1) development of the live radiation-attenuated vaccine against cattle lungworm, *Dictyocaulus viviparus*, which continues as a marketed product to today; (2) insights into the development of the radiation-attenuated dog hookworm vaccine against *Ancylostoma caninum* and why this vaccine was never licensed; (3) the development and field testing of the candidate radiation-attenuated vaccine against *Schistosoma bovis* (and other schistosomes); (4) establishment of the cGMP methodology for radiation-attenuation of *Plasmodium falciparum* sporozoites and manufacture of PfSPZ Vaccine for use in Phase-2 clinical trials together with the recent groundbreaking results for the vaccine in women of

childbearing potential in Mali; (5) the methodology for converting the cGMP irradiation of PfSPZ using gamma irradiation to a cGMP process for X-ray irradiation; and (6) the importance of developing appropriate thermostabilization method(s) and distribution logistics for live vaccines, and the science behind cryopreservation used in the stabilization of eukaryotic live radiation-attenuated vaccines.

Using radiation-inducible promoters to produce vaccinal proteins

Balkiss Bouhaouala-Zahar is a prominent Tunisian molecular biologist and immuno-biochemist, specializing in recombinant protein-based immunotherapy and vaccine development. She has received numerous accolades, including the Medal for Rendered Services awarded at the International Course on Health Support in Saharan Environments (March 2009, Tozeur, Tunisia), a Gold Medal at the 4th Korea International Women's Invention Exposition (May 2011, Seoul, Korea), and a Special Prize from the Intellectual Property Poland Office (September 2016). She won the National Innovation Contest (May 2016) and was selected for a Fellowship in the ANDI-EMORY University joint program for Project-Based Training through the African Network for Drugs and Diagnostics Innovation (July 2017). Since November 2013, she has been a Fellow of the African Academy of Sciences (FAAS). Throughout her career, she has made significant contributions to biomedical research, notably in the development of next-generation antivenoms, such as NbF12-10 chimeric candidate, targeting scorpion and cobra envenomations through projects funded by NATO and the Wellcome Trust, as well as recombinant antigen-based vaccines, including a ZZ-fused vaccinal toxin developed under the CEA-funded initiative. Her research also includes the development of nanobody-based immune modulators targeting Tenascin-C and ion channel functions, as part of the Tunisia PromESsE program funded by the World Bank. She currently leads the NanoBioMedika research team at the LBVAT Lab (IPT) and actively contributes to the development of irradiation-based recombinant vaccines under IAEA-funded R&D projects (<http://www.aquavac-ir.tn/>). Her expertise encompasses biosensor development for targeted biomarkers. She is a member of the National CNEARS Committee, responsible for evaluating research laboratory

programs and project proposals, providing strategic research guidance to the Ministries of Higher Education and Scientific Research and Health in Tunisia. She earned her doctoral degree in Molecular and Cellular Biology from the University of Tunis El Manar in 1997, demonstrating the efficacy of a recombinant ZZ-fused toxin in inducing a protective immune response against lethal doses of scorpion venom. She has specialized knowledge in patentability, having obtained certifications in intellectual property and licensing from WIPO and UC Davis (2008 and 2012, respectively).

During the workshop, she conducted a practical session titled “Using radiation-inducible promoters to produce vaccinal proteins,” with key “take-home” messages including: (1) advanced techniques in the development of VLP-based vaccines which are increasingly recognized as safe and effective next-generation of vaccines against prevalent and emergent diseases; (2) main characteristics and advantages of non-replicative, non-infectious and irradiation-based VLP vaccines for producing immunogenic and vaccinal compositions; (3) step-by-step guide for utilizing toolkits and software for *in silico* constructions of recombinant vectors, including the methodology of inserting a radiation-inducible promoter (e.g., SOS-like box) and a sequence encoding a recombinant immunogenic vaccinal protein; (4) the upstream overall process of protein production induced by irradiation and the downstream process of purification; and (5) the method of obtaining self-assembled VLP particles with repetitive structures and patterns that are recognized by the immune systems.

AI: Immunogenicity and reactogenicity of vaccines’ signatures prediction

Mohamed Ould Elhassen Aoueilyine is a member of the IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Society (GRSS) with expertise in embedded systems, artificial intelligence, and IoT cloud development. He earned his Ph.D. in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in 2014 from the Higher School of Communications of Tunis (SUPCOM), Carthage University, Tunisia. He is a member of the IAEA TC Project TUN5032 (<http://www.aquavac-ir.tn/>). His key areas of expertise include IoT nanosatellites, Linux programming, LoRa

technology, and the application of artificial intelligence for vaccine signature prediction.

During this workshop, he conducted a practical session entitled "AI: Immunogenicity and reactogenicity of vaccines' signatures prediction."

Metabolic networks modelling based on post-vaccination omic data

Alia Benkahla is a bioinformaticist at the Institut Pasteur de Tunis, specializing in bioinformatics, biomathematics, and biostatistics, with an initial academic background in mathematics. She pursued her Ph.D. at the Institute of Genetics and Molecular and Cellular Biology (IGSCNRS) in Marseille, followed by a postdoctoral fellowship at the Max Planck Institute in Berlin. Since joining the Institut Pasteur de Tunis in 2005, she has made significant contributions to the field by founding and leading the Bioinformatics and Mathematical Modeling Group, focusing on capacity building through student training and co-organizing international events in Africa. Her research primarily addresses systems biology, particularly the regulatory processes involved in diseases such as leishmaniasis and tuberculosis. She has also served as the President of the African Society of Bioinformatics and Computational Biology from 2015 to 2019 and currently leads the "Metabolic networks modelling" process within the IAEA TC Project TUN5032 (<http://www.aquavac-ir.tn/>).

In this workshop, she conducted a practical session titled "Metabolic networks modelling based on post-vaccination omic data."

Generation of inactivated vaccines by low-energy electron irradiation

Sebastian Ulbert is a prominent expert in vaccine development, pathogen inactivation, serological diagnostics, and virology, currently serving as the Deputy Director of the Fraunhofer Institute for Cell Therapy and Immunology (IZI) in Leipzig, Germany, where he also leads the BSL-3 facility and the Department of Vaccines and Infection Models. His academic credentials include a PhD from the Netherlands Cancer Institute and postdoctoral research at EMBL Heidelberg, alongside a habilitation at the Medical Faculty of the

University of Leipzig, where he lectures on "Experimental Virology." He has successfully secured substantial funding through various national and international grants, including projects with the Eurostars FLAVICURE initiative and the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, while also coordinating the Fraunhofer MAVO consortium ELVIRA and multiple EU projects. His scholarly contributions comprise 68 publications in PubMed, focusing on serological responses to infectious diseases such as SARS-CoV-2, West Nile virus, and Dengue virus, as well as numerous patents in vaccine development and virus inactivation technologies. Additionally, he serves on the editorial board of Clinical and Experimental Vaccine Research and as an advisory board member for KyooBe Tech GmbH, while collaborating with the IAEA as an external expert.

In this workshop, he led a session titled "Generation of inactivated vaccines by low-energy electron irradiation (LEEI)," which conveyed key "take-home" messages including: (1) LEEI generates highly efficient vaccine candidates and can be applied in biological laboratories or pharmaceutical production facilities, as only minimal shielding constructions are required; (2) LEEI is also suitable to sterilize biological liquids such as serum for the use in pharmaceutical production processes; (3) when planning projects on irradiated vaccines, the required dose has to be determined for every pathogen individually; (4) suitable controls for studies with irradiated vaccines include the chemically inactivated preparation.

Independent quality control concept of veterinary vaccines in Africa and initiative for a harmonized regulatory framework for vaccine registration and inspection of vaccine manufacturers in Africa

Charles S. Bodjo is a Doctor of Veterinary Medicine (DVM) from the École Nationale Vétérinaire de Lyon and the Faculté de Médecine, Université Claude Bernard, Lyon, France. He holds a Master of Science (MSc) in Bacteriology-Virology from the University of Abidjan-Cocody, Côte d'Ivoire, and a PhD in Virology from Université de Montpellier II, France. Additionally, he has obtained Diplomas in General Immunology and Medical Virology from the Pasteur

Institute in Paris, France. He has over 25 years of experience in vaccine research and development, as well as in the development of serological diagnostic tests. His expertise extends to laboratory biorisk management. He served as the Head of Viral Diseases Diagnosis and Sero-monitoring of Rinderpest at the Laboratoire Central de Pathologie Animale in Bingerville, Côte d'Ivoire, from 1995 to 2003. Subsequently, he acted as a Consultant Scientist at the FAO/IAEA Biotechnology Laboratory in Austria, where he focused on developing marker vaccines and companion tests for Peste des Petits Ruminants (PPR) from 2003 to 2009. Since joining the African Union pan African Veterinary vaccine Centre (AU-PANVAC) in 2009 as the Senior Animal Disease Diagnosis Reagents Officer, he has led laboratory research to develop several diagnostic tools currently utilized in African Union Member States for the control and surveillance of animal diseases. He also supervises the quality control of veterinary vaccine activities, oversees research projects, and mentors students in PhD, Master's, and internship programs at AU-PANVAC. Presently, he serves as the Acting Director of AU-PANVAC and as an Associate Professor at PAULESI, where he teaches courses on biorisk management (biosafety and biosecurity). He is actively involved in designing and implementing animal disease control programs across Africa and participates in various scientific committees.

In this workshop, he led two sessions titled "Independent veterinary vaccine quality control concept in Africa" and "Support in harmonization of standards in Africa for vaccine registration," which highlighted critical "take-home" messages including:

- The concept of independent quality control of veterinary vaccines in Africa has led the establishment of the AU-PANVAC and its achievements improved the quality of vaccines from 20 to 90% presently. AU-PANVAC supports also activities on validation of new vaccines.
- The second presentation was on "AU-PANVAC Support for the initiative for a harmonized regulatory framework for vaccine registration and inspection of vaccine manufacturers in Africa". This initiative aims to facilitate mutual

acceptance of quality standards in line with the objective of the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA).

- As a future role with the new mandate, AU-PANVAC, in collaboration with National Regulatory Authorities (NRAs) in Africa, will audit and certify vaccine manufacturers. The Centre in collaboration with AU-IBAR, is going to establish a network of African regulatory authorities for capacity building and information exchanges. AU-PANVAC is also considering the possibility of establishing a continental vaccino-vigilance platform to monitor vaccine safety and efficacy, potential adverse events and substandard products.

Tunisia's high energy electron beam accelerator

Mokhtar Kraïem, head of the Ionizing Radiation Sub-Directorate, CNSTN, Tunisia, possesses specialized expertise in radiation technologies, with a focus on the applications of cobalt-60 for radiation processes and extensive knowledge of electron beam technology for industrial applications.

In this workshop, he led a session entitled "Tunisia's high energy electron beam accelerator," where he emphasized key insights including an overview of Tunisia's existing irradiation infrastructure which includes two irradiators: a pilot scale cobalt-60 gamma irradiator (maximum capacity 100 kCi) and a HEEB accelerator (5 to 10 MeV, 5 kW). Throughout his speech, he detailed the main characteristics of the electron accelerator installation (building, main and auxiliary equipment) and the principal applications/uses and work carried out using this accelerator. Finally, he presented the details of the irradiations carried out by the electron accelerator for the generation of inactivated vaccines.

Ethical issues arising from preclinical vaccine trials

Ouajdi Souilem obtained his Doctor of Veterinary Medicine from the National Veterinary School in Sidi Thabet, Tunisia, in 1986, followed by a PhD in Pharmacology from the University of Nantes, France, in 1998. He has served as a Professor of Physiology and Pharmacology since 2001. Since 1998, he has held the position of Tunisian National Representative at the International Council for Laboratory Animal Science (ICLAS) and has served as the Acting

Chair of the ICLAS Africa Region Committee from 2019 to 2023. He is also responsible for liaison activities with the World Health Organization (WHO). His professional background includes membership on the *Ad Hoc* Committee of Laboratory Animal Welfare at the World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE) and WHO in Paris from 2007 to 2011, and he is the Founding President of the Tunisian Association for Laboratory Animal Science (ATSAL), established in 2007. Additionally, he served as the President of the National Committee on Ethics in Animal Experimentation under the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research in Tunisia from 2017 to 2020. He currently serves as the Acting President of the Animal Ethics Committee (AEC/IACUC) at the National Veterinary School of Sidi Thabet and is a member of the international initiative ONE WELFARE PHOENIX. He is also the Tunisian coordinator for the Twinning OIE project, collaborating with IZSAM in Italy, titled "Animal Welfare in Tunisia and North Africa" (2021–2024), which aims to establish a WHO collaborating centre for animal welfare in North Africa. In November 2022, he was appointed as the Chief Executive Officer of BiotechPole Sidi Thabet, a technopark dedicated to the health and pharmaceutical industry in Tunisia.

During this workshop, he led a session on “Ethical issues arising from preclinical vaccine trials,” wherein he presented key take-home messages, including:

(1) Role of the preclinical phase: The preclinical phase of vaccine development focuses on evaluating a vaccine's safety and efficacy in animal models, without involving human subjects. This phase is crucial for determining the vaccine's ability to induce immunity and prevent disease.

(2) Advantages of animal models: Animal studies offer valuable insights into the virus's replication capacity, tissue tropism, and kinetic response. This helps researchers understand the vaccine's effectiveness in controlling infection and potential adverse effects.

(3) Ethical considerations in animal research: Preclinical testing follows the universally accepted "3R" principles:

- o Replacement: Whenever possible, scientists should replace the use of animals with alternative non-animal methods.

- o Reduction: Efforts should be made to minimize the number of animals used in experiments while still obtaining reliable data.
 - o Refinement: Researchers should refine experimental techniques to reduce pain, distress, and suffering in animals. This includes improving housing, care, and environmental enrichment to support the animals' welfare. These principles emphasize the balance between scientific rigor and ethical responsibility in the preclinical evaluation of vaccines.
- (4) Animal welfare in research: Scientists must ensure that animals are provided with appropriate living conditions, including adequate housing, nutrition, and care. Animal welfare is integral to maintaining their physiological and behavioral needs, ultimately improving the quality and reliability of the research.
- (5) Protocol submission to Animal Ethics Committee (AEC) for preclinical testing approval: The scientist must submit his protocol to an AEC for ethical review before starting the preclinical testing.

Success story from Iran

Farahnaz Motamedi Sedeh is a leading Iranian microbiologist and virologist specializing in molecular biology, vaccinology, and immunology. She led six vaccine research and development projects, and all six projects resulted in the production of eight different types of vaccines for animals and humans. Three types of vaccines against white spot syndrome virus (WSSV) have been developed: (1) a gamma-irradiated WSSV vaccine, (2) an electron-irradiated vaccine, and (3) a formalin-inactivated vaccine to protect *Litopenaeus vannamei* against WSSV. Two other types of tetravalent FMD vaccines have been produced to protect cattle against the FMD virus, including (4) a gamma-irradiated tetravalent FMD vaccine and (5) an electron beam tetravalent FMD vaccine. Moreover, she and her team produced (6) a gamma-irradiated avian influenza virus of subtype H9N2 on broiler chickens, (7) a gamma-irradiated human influenza virus of subtype H1N1, and finally (8) a gamma-irradiated inactivated polio vaccine. She collaborated with the Joint FAO/IAEA Department in Vienna as DTM of a regional project RAS5085 for the use of nuclear techniques for the detection of priority animal diseases and zoonotic diseases. This project aimed to strengthen the capacity to detect and

differentiate priority animal diseases and zoonotic diseases threatening poultry and livestock production and public health in Asia through the collaboration of twenty Asian countries. She was able to show that gamma-irradiated H9N2 avian influenza virus is a successful vaccine that induces humoral and cellular immune responses and cytokine responses in broiler chickens. She reported different formulations for this vaccine and showed that the formulated vaccine with trehalose in the intranasal route of administration induced the highest immune responses and it has stability in 4 and -70°C after 12 months. She received a grant to work on the irradiated FMD vaccine and a DNA vaccine based on the VP1 gene. She showed that a gamma-irradiated FMD vaccine can induce a neutralizing antibody response in cattle, as can a conventional FMD vaccine, and that the use of these two FMD vaccines in a prime-boost strategy can upregulate Th1 and Th2 cytokines. She plays a key role in the development of nuclear techniques for vaccine and animal disease development. Since 2012, she has been an assistant professor at the Nuclear Science and Technology Research Institute (NSTRI) in Iran, and then as an associate professor where she served as head of the Department of Veterinary and Animal Sciences. She has been a member of several national and international advisory boards and committees, both academic and governmental, including the National Institute for Vaccine and Serum Research and the Iran Veterinary Organization.

In this workshop, she presented the success story of her team and collaborators, wherein she presented key take-home messages, including:

- (1) The irradiated vaccine team in Iran has over ten years of experience in the research and development of several animal and human vaccines with the collaboration of five national institutes and a university including, the Nuclear Science and Technology Research Institute, Razi Vaccine and Serum Research Institute, Iran Veterinary Organization, Pasteur Institute of Iran, Iran Fishery Science Research Institute, and Tarbiat Modares University.
- (2) The findings of immune responses that were induced by the irradiated avian Influenza vaccine on broiler chicken showed induction of cellular immunity, mucosal immunity as well as humoral immunity, and a protective response

against homologous challenge with live virus, and stability of vaccine till 12 months.

(3) The scientists of Iran's irradiated vaccine team wrote the Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for producing various irradiated vaccines including Foot and Mouth diseases Virus (two formulations; Gamma Irradiated Tetravalent FMD vaccine and Electron Beam Irradiated Tetravalent FMD Vaccine), White Spot Syndrome Virus (three formulations; Gamma Irradiated WSSV vaccine, Electron Beam Irradiated WSSV vaccine, and Formalin WSSV Vaccine), Avian Influenza Virus (H9N2) (two formulations; Gamma Irradiated AIV-H9N2 plus Trehalose-IN, Gamma Irradiated AIV-H9N2 plus Oil ISA70-SC), Gamma Irradiated Human Influenza Vaccine (H1N1) plus Trehalose-IN, Gamma Irradiated Polio Virus plus Trehalose.

Success story from Tunisia

Nadia Cherif has served as the head of the Aquatic Animal Health Viral Diagnostic Section at the National Institute of Sea Sciences and Technologies (INSTM) in Tunisia since 2010, following the completion of her PhD in microbiology with a specialization in fish virology. Her primary research focus is on the development of effective preventive and control measures for fish pathogens, which are of critical importance to fish farmers. Under her leadership, her team actively participates in the establishment of a national zoo-sanitary control network, the implementation of a biosecurity program, and the monitoring of prevalent diseases within marine farming sites. Her expertise includes the testing of aquatic species for pathogens listed by the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH), as well as other significant viral agents responsible for substantial economic losses in marine aquaculture. Her team offers tailored support to farmers by providing targeted technical services to address specific issues and unexplained mortality events. Furthermore, her laboratory conducts regular surveys and assessments of the zoo-sanitary conditions of aquatic farms, assisting farmers in the adoption of prophylactic practices concerning biosecurity measures. Additionally, her efforts support the integration of public-private partnership (PPP) initiatives to enhance the role of veterinary services and laboratories within the aquaculture sector. Recently, she has joined various national and international organizations as a member of

several technical groups. Notably, she has served as a member of the national committee for zoo-sanitary agreement validation and the national committee for the approval of veterinary vaccines since 2020. Furthermore, she has been a consultant within the African Union InterAfrican Bureau for Animal Resources (AU-IBAR) as part of the Aquatic Animal Health Expert Group, where she prepares comments and African common positions on draft WOAHP chapters since 2021. Additionally, she holds a consulting role within the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM). In 2022, she was appointed as the head of the Technical Activity Group (TAG) for Aquatic Animal Health and Biosecurity within the GFCM region. Currently, she leads the "Virus production and titration, fish immunity and fish experiments in general" process within two IAEA-funded Projects (<http://www.aquavac-ir.tn/>).

During this workshop, she presented the success stories of her team and collaborators, highlighting several key take-home messages, including:

- (1) The use of irradiation to develop as an effective and safe vaccine against nodavirus represents a significant breakthrough in fish health management, reducing the risk of disease outbreaks and ensuring sustainable aquaculture practices, enhancing the productivity and profitability of fish farming industries.
- (2) Gamma irradiation inactivates pathogens without altering their structure, allowing the vaccine to trigger a strong immune response without the risk of reverting to a virulent form and reduce the risk of leaving harmful residues in fish or the environment, making them safer for both consumers and ecosystems. These vaccines can be produced relatively cheaply, with irradiation technology being scalable and efficient, contributing to cost-effective disease management in aquaculture.
- (3) The significant breakthrough achieved through the use of radiation-inducible promoters, enabling the successful production of self-assembled VLPs. These VLPs, characterized by their repetitive structures and patterns, were effectively recognized by the immune system, reaffirming their potential as highly promising immunogenic and vaccinal candidates.
- (4) *In silico* tools are crucial for predicting immunogenicity and determining metabolic networks in the context of vaccine development and administration, particularly in fields like aquaculture; reducing time and costs compared to

traditional experimental methods. In addition, computational models can simulate the fish immune system, providing insights into how a vaccine might perform *in vivo*, helping refine formulations before conducting expensive and time-consuming trials.

Conclusions

The workshop concluded with a Closing Ceremony on Friday, 20 September 2024, which featured presentations on success stories and the distribution of diplomas. The event served as an invaluable platform for scientific exchange and collaboration, advancing the application of irradiation techniques in vaccine development throughout the Arab region. A key recommendation emerging from the workshop is the development and implementation, in collaboration with key stakeholders, of an Arab strategy for the peaceful use of atomic energy in the development of irradiated vaccines.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Authors' contributions

HS: Conceptualization, original draft preparation, review, and editing.

BB: Review and editing with contribution to original draft preparation.

NC: Review and editing with contribution to original draft preparation.

RTK: Review and editing with contribution to original draft preparation.

MOEA: Review and editing with contribution to original draft preparation.

DB: Review and editing with contribution to original draft preparation.

AB: Review and editing with contribution to original draft preparation.

MK: Review and editing with contribution to original draft preparation.

OS: Review and editing with contribution to original draft preparation.

SCB: Review and editing with contribution to original draft preparation.

FMS: Review and editing with contribution to original draft preparation.

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VW: Review and editing with contribution to original draft preparation.
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References

Wijewardana, V., Ulbert, S., and Cattoli, G. (2022). Editorial: Irradiation technologies for vaccine development. *Frontiers in immunology* 13, 1075335.

Additional files

Additional folder 1 – Presentations and data.

Presentations and data of the workshop on the "Development of irradiated vaccines", 16–20/09/2024, Republic of Tunisia, are available upon request.